

**AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF PAKSHAGHATA W.S.R TO
HEMIPLEGIA - A REVIEW****¹Dr. Satya Narayan Sahu, ²Dr. Sonalika Jena, ³Dr. Bharatilata Acharya**¹PG Scholar, PG Department of Kayachikitsa, GAM, Puri(Odisha).²Associate Professor, PG Department of Kayachikitsa, GAM, Puri(Odisha).³Assistant Professor, PG Department of Kayachikitsa, GAM, Puri(Odisha).Article Received on
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Accepted on 23 Sept. 2025,<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17223891>***Corresponding Author****Dr. Satya Narayan Sahu**PG Scholar, PG Department
of Kayachikitsa, GAM,
Puri(Odisha).**ABSTRACT**

Pakshaghata is a Vata dosha predominant disease. It has been enlisted among the Eighty Vataja Nanatmaja Vikara and considered as a Mahavatavyadhi in Ayurvedic textual literature. Pakshaghata is the condition in which the aggaravated vata dosha, invades the shareera dhamanis and disupts the functions of Sira (Blood vessels), Snayu (Ligaments) and Kandara (Tendon) causing loss of function of one side of the body. It can be compared to Hemiplegia (paralysis) from modern perspective, which is the commonest manifestation of Cerebro Vascular Accident (CVA) or stroke. Stroke or CVA is defined as the rapid onset of focal neurological deficit, resulting from diseases of the cerebral vasculature and its contents 85% is ischemic and 15% are primary hemorrhage, affecting the face, limbs and trunk on one side of the boby.

According to the World Health Organization, 15 million people suffer stroke worldwide each year, of these, 5 million die another 5 5 million are permanently disable. According to modern science, once brain tissue is irreversibly damaged, it cannot be regenerated through conventional therapies, often resulting in lasting neurological deficit and a poor prognosis, ultimately rendering the patient dependent and disabled. This article aims to explore the aetiopathogenesis, clinical presentation, and management of the disease based on Ayurvedic classics, thereby offering a foundational reference for emerging practitioners in addressing this challenging condition.

KEYWORDS: Pakshaghata, Vatavyadhi, Hemiplegia, Stroke, Cerebrovascular accident, aetiopathogenesis.

INTRODUCTION

Pakshaghata is a Vata dosha predominant disease. It has been enlisted among the Eighty Vataja Nanatmaja Vikara^[1] and considered as a Mahavatavyadhi^[2] in Ayurvedic textual literature. The term Pakshaghata is the combination of two words i.e Paksha and Aghata. The word “Paksha” denotes either half of the body and “Aghata” denotes the impairment of Karmendriyas and Gyanendriyas. Karmendriyas are considered as part of the motor system and Gyanendriyas are considered as part of the sensory system. So the term Pakshaghata literally means, “Paralysis of one half of the body”. According to Maharsri Charak the Vata dosha get aggravated by various Vataprakopaka Nidana like Virudha Aahara, Atijagarana, Ati Vyavaya, Asruk Srava, Vichesta, Dhatu Kshya, Shoka, Chinta, Marmabhighata and Vegasandharana. Then the aggravated vata dosha, invades the shareera dhamanis and disrupts the functions of Sira (Blood vessels), Snayu (Ligaments) and Kandara (Tendon)causing loss of function of one side of the body and initiates pathogenesis of Pakshaghata. Acharya Sushruta explained that Vata Dosha travels in Urdhava Adhoga Tiryaka Dhamani and causes Sandhi Bandhana Moksha that ultimately leads to loss of function in one half of body called Pakshaghata. Prognosis of the disease as mentioned by Sushruta is Sadhya when Vata Dosha associated with other Dosha, Krichhrasadhya when purely Vata is involved and Asadhya when Dhatukshaya is responsible for Pakshaghata.

Pakshaghata can be correlated with the disease Hemiplegia which is the commonest manifestation of Cerebrovascular accidents(CVA) or Stroke. Stroke is the sudden death of some brain cells due to lack of oxygen when the blood flow to the brain is lost by blockage or rupture of an artery to the brain. Modern science described age, arteriosclerosis, injury, hemorrhage, nutrition imbalance and anxiety as causative factors of disease. The most common symptom of a stroke is sudden weakness or numbness of the face, arm or leg, most often on one side of the body. Other symptoms include: confusion, difficulty in speaking, difficulty in vision with one or both eyes; difficulty in walking, dizziness, loss of balance or coordination. Cerebrovascular accidents(CVA) known as strokes, are divided into two categories: A blockage causes an ischemic stroke, while a blood vessel rupture causes a hemorrhagic stroke. Both types of strokes deprive a section of the brain of blood and oxygen, resulting in the death of brain cells. Ischemic strokes are the most prevalent form, accounting for around 80% of all strokes. According to the World Health Organization, 15 million people suffer stroke worldwide each year, of these, 5 million die and another 5 million are permanently disabled.^[4] The prevalence of stroke in India is approximately 200 per 1 lakh

people.^[5] This disease has posed a great problem to the medical field as far as its treatment is concerned. Modern science believes that the brain tissues once damaged completely cannot be repaired by the therapies leading to permanent neurological deficit. Hence, the disease has a poor prognosis, making the person disabled and dependent. This article aims to explore the aetiopathogenesis, clinical presentation, and management of the disease based on Ayurvedic classics, thereby offering a foundational reference for emerging practitioners in addressing this challenging condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ayurvedic review of literature categorized under

- 1) Etymology
- 2) Nidan Panchak
- 3) Sadhya Asadhyata
- 4) Pathophysiological
- 5) Chikitsa
- 6) Pathya Apathya

1) ETYMOLOGY

The term Pakshaghata itself reflects the principal clinical manifestation of the disease.

The word Pakshaghata derived from Shashthi Tat Purusha Samaas^[6]

‘Pakshsya Dehangasya Ghaatam Vinashanam Yasmaat Yatra Vaa’^[7]

Synonyms - Pakshavadha, Pakshagraha, Pakshavata, Ardhangavata, Ardhangasosha, and Pakshahata

In the listed synonyms, the term Paksha— meaning "side" or "flank"—remains constant, while the suffixes such as -Aghata, -Ghaata, and -Vadha differ. The suffixes Aghata and Ghata imply "Hanan" (to strike or kill), whereas Vadha denotes killing, destruction, or paralysis.

2) NIDAN PANCHAK OF PAKSHAGHATA NIDAN

A review of Ayurvedic literature reveals that no specific causative factors are exclusively mentioned for Pakshaghata. Instead, it is understood that all factors responsible for vitiating Vata Dosha can be considered the root causes of this condition. The Nidana (etiological factors) described for Vata Vyadhi in classical texts can be systematically categorized as follows:

1. *Aharajanya (Dietary) Factors*

These include dietary habits, the nature of consumed food, and improper food combinations that aggravate Vata Dosha.^[8,9,10,11,12,13]

2. *Viharajanya (Behavioral) Factors*

This category encompasses daily activities and lifestyle choices that are known to provoke Vata Dosha.^[14,15,16]

3. *Manasajanya (Psychological) Factors*

Emotional states such as Chinta (anxiety), Shoka (grief), Kama (desire), Krodha (anger), and Bhaya (fear) disturb the balance of Vata Dosha.

4. *Abhigataj (Traumatic) Factors: Physical trauma or injury that leads to the aggravation of Vata Dosha.*^[17-22]

5. *Anya (Miscellaneous) Factors*

Other causative aspects like seasonal variations, overuse of purification therapies (Shodhana), and irregular routines that disturb Vata Dosha.^[23-25]

Tabular Presentation of etiological factors as,

Table 1: Aharajanya (Dietary) Factors vitiating Vata Dosha.

SI No.	Factor	C.S.	S.S.	A.S.	A.H.	SI No.	Factor	C.S.	S.S.	A.S.	A.H.
1	Ruksha	+	+	+	+	16	Nishpava		+		
2	Sheeta	+	+	+	+	17	Vallura		+		
3	Laghu	+	+	+	+	18	Trunadhanya			+	+
4	Katu	+	+	+	+	19	Virudhaka			+	+
5	Tikita	+	+	+	+	20	Tumba			+	+
6	Kashaya	+	+	+	+	21	Shaluka			+	+
7	Rukshashaka		+			22	Jambava			+	+
8	Uddalaka		+			23	Adhyashana		+		
9	Koradusha		+			24	Vishamashana		+		
10	Shyamaka		+			25	Alpa/Pramit Anna	+		+	+
11	Mudga		+			26	Laghu Anna	+		+	
12	Masura		+			27	Langhan	+			
13	Adhaki		+			28	AbhojanaAnnashan	+	+		
14	Harenu		+			29	Vishamashana		+		
15	Kalaya		+			30	Adhyashana		+		

Table 2: Viharjanya (Behavioral) Factors vitiating Vata Dosha.

Sl No.	Factor	C.S.	S.S.	A.S.	A.H.	Sl No.	Factor	C. S.	S. S.	A. S.	A.H.
1	Ativyavaya	+	+	+	+	11	Ati vicheshta	+			
2	Ati Prajagaran	+	+	+	+	12	Bharavahana	+	+		
3	Plavana	+	+			13	Vegasandharana	+	+	+	+
4	Pratarana		+	+		14	Uchchabhashana	+		+	+
5	Adhava gaman	+		+		15	Gajaticharya		+	+	
6	Ativyayama	+	+	+	+	16	Turangaticharya		+		
7	Dukhashaiyya	+				17	Ratha-aticharya		+		
8	Dukha-asana	+				18	Pada aticharya		+		
9	Divaswapna	+				19	Pradhavana	+		+	
10	Atiadyayana		+	+		20	Kshudhita ambupana			+	

Table 3: Manasajanya (Psychological) Factors vitiating Vata Dosha.

Sr.	Factor	C.S.	S.S.	A.S.	A.H.	Sr.	Factor	C. S.	S. S.	A. S.	A.H.
1	Chinta	+			+	4	Bhaya	+			+
2	Shoka	+		+	+	5	Kama	+			
3	Krodha	+				6	Apravritta Vega Udirana			+	+

Table 4: Abhigatjanya (Traumatic) Factors vitiating Vata Dosha.

Sl No.	Factor	C.S.	S.S.	A.S.	A.H.	Sl No.	Factor	C. S.	S. S.	A. S.	A.H.
1	Abhigata	+	+	+		4	Prapatan	+	+		
2	Marmaghata	+				5	Prapidan/ Prahar		+		
3	Balvad Vighraha			+	+						

Table 5: Anya (Miscellaneous) Factors vitiating Vata Dosha.

Sl No.	Factor	C.S.	S.S.	A.S.	A.H.	Sl No.	Factor	C. S.	S. S.	A. S.	A.H.
1	Pravata		+			11	Pragvata			+	
2	Grishma Ante			+	+	12	Dhatu Kshaya	+			
3	Jeerna Ante		+			13	Rogati Karshanam	+			
4	Ahoratri Ante			+	+	14	Aama	+			
5	Varsha Rutu	+	+	+	+	15	Margasyaavarana	+		+	+
6	Bhukta Ante				+	16	Vishama Upachar	+			
7	Shita Kala		+			17	Ati Dosha Stravana	+	+		
8	Abhara		+			18	Ati Asrika Stravana	+	+	+	
9	Prabhat Kala		+			19	Kriyati Yoga /			+	+
10	Aparahan		+	+		20	Vaya	+	+	+	+

POORVARUPA

The Poorvarupa (prodromal symptoms) of Pakshaghata are not specifically described in classical Ayurvedic texts. However, since Pakshaghata is categorized under Vata Vyadhi, the

general Poorvarupa of Vata disorders may be applicable. Acharya Charaka has described *Avyakta Lakshana* as the prodromal signs of Vata Vyadhi, which can be considered relevant here.^[26]

RUPA

Various symptoms of Pakshaghata described in Ayurvedic literatures are,^[27-30]

Table 6: Representing Symptoms of Pakshaghata.

Sl No.	Factor	C.S.	S.S	A.S.	A.H.
1	Anyatara Paksha Chesta Nivritti	+	+	+	+
2	Anyatara Pakshahanan	+	+	+	+
3	Achetana		+	+	+
4	Akarmanyata		+	+	+
5	Hasta Pada Sankocha	+			
6	Sira Snayu Vishosha	+		+	+
7	Vak Stambha	+			
8	Ruja	+			
9	Toda	+			
10	Shoola	+			
11	Sandhibandha Vimoksha		+	+	+
12	Daha, Santap, Moorcha		+		
13	Shaitya, Shopha, Gurutva		+		

SAMPRAPTI

The Samprapti of Pakshaghata can be conventionally understood in two forms:

A) *Sāmānya Samprapti (General Pathogenesis)*

As per Acharya Charaka, due to various causative factors, Vata Dosha becomes vitiated and accumulates in the Rikta Srotas (empty channels), resulting in different types of Vata Vyadhi, including Pakshaghata. The vitiation of Vata occurs through two primary mechanisms:^[31]

a) *Dhatukshaya (Tissue Depletion)*

Practices such as excessive fasting (Langhana), intake of light and dry food (Laghu, Ruksha Ahara), and excessive sexual activity (Atimaituna) lead to depletion of Dhatus like **Rasa** and **Shukra**, causing Rikta Srotas and subsequent Vata Prakopa.

b) Margavarana (Obstruction of Pathways): Factors such as Ama, Vegasandharana (suppression of natural urges), and Marmaghata (trauma) cause obstruction in the body channels.

This results in partial or complete Margavarana, leading to Vata vitiation beyond the point of obstruction. This represents Sanga type of Srotodushti.

B) *Vishista Samprapti (Specific Pathogenesis) of Pakshaghata*

The classical Ayurvedic Samhita outline specific Samprapti for Pakshaghata, detailing its manifestation by different Acharyas:

a) CharakaSamhita

Acharya Charaka explains that vitiated Vata Dosha localizes on either the left or right side of the body. It causes *dryness in the Sira (vessels) and Snayu (ligaments)*, resulting in loss of movement, stiffness (*Vakstambha*), pain (*Ruja*), and contraction(*Sankocha*) of the affected limbs.^[32]

b) SushrutaSamhita

Acharya Sushruta describes that aggravated Vata traverses through the *Urdhvaga, Adhoga, and Tiryaka Dhamanis* (ascending, descending, and transverse vessels), causing loosening of joint structures (*Sandhi Bandha*). This leads to sudden paralysis (*Paksha Hani*) of either the left or right half of the body, often accompanied by loss of sensation, sudden collapse, or even death.^[33]

c) Ashtanga Sangraha & Ashtanga Hridaya Vagbhata integrates both Charaka's and Sushruta's views, stating that Vata affects one half of the body, dries the Sira and Snayu, loosens joints, and renders the body functionless(*Ardhakaya Akarmanyata*) with loss of consciousness (*Vichetana*).^[34,35]

Factors involved in Samprapti of Pakshaghata^[39]

Doshas	:	Vata (All five types; Prana, Udana Vayu especially)
	:	Pitta (Panchak Pitta, Ranjak Pitta especially)
	:	Kapha (Shleshak and Avalambaka Kapha especially)
Dushyas	:	Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda Dhatu and Manas
Agni	:	Jatharaagni, Dhatvaagni
Ama	:	Dhatwaagni-Maandya-Janya
Strotasa	:	Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, and Medavaha
Strotodushti	:	Atipravrutti, Sanga, Siraagranthi & Vimaarga Gamana Udbhava
Sthana	:	Pakwaashaya
Sanchara Sthana	:	Urdhwa, Adhah, Tiryak Dhamanis
Adhithana	:	Shira
Rogamarga	:	Madhyam Roga marga
Vyakti Sthana	:	Either Dakshin or Vama Paksha

3) *Sādhyā-Asādhyatva (Prognosis)*

Before commencing the treatment of any disease, its prognosis must be assessed. The curability of Pakshaghata (hemiplegia) as described in classical Ayurvedic texts varies based on causative factors and patient strength.

Charaka Samhita^[40,41]

Charaka categorizes Pakshaghata as *Kashta Sadhya* (difficult to cure) or *Asadhya* (incurable). If the condition is of recent onset, uncomplicated, and the patient is strong (*Balawan*), there is potential for cure. Otherwise, the prognosis is poor.

Sushruta Samhita^[42]

Shuddha Vataja type – *Krichhra Sadhya* (difficult to cure)

Samsrushta Doshaja type – *Sadhya* (Curable) *Dhatu Kshaya* type – *Asadhya* (incurable)

Ashtanga Sangraha and Hridayam^[43,44] Acharya Vagbhata states:

Shuddha Vataja type – *Krichhra Sadhyatama* (extremely difficult to cure)

Samsrushta Doshaja type – *Krichhra Sadhya* (difficult but curable)

Kshaya Nimittaja type – *Asadhya* (incurable)

4) *Chikitsa (Therapeutic Approaches in Pakshaghata)*

The Ayurvedic classics offer varied yet complementary approaches to the management of Pakshaghata. The emphasis is primarily on *Snehana*, *Swedana*, *Shodhana*, and *Basti*, tailored to the stage and constitution of the patient.

Charaka Samhita^[45]

Acharya Charaka prescribes *Swedana* (sudation), *Snehana* (oleation), and *Virechana* (purgation) as key interventions. Commentators like Jejjata and Gangadhara interpret this as *Snehayukta Swedana* (oleation-based sudation) and *Snehayukta Virechana* (purgation with unctuous substances), indicating the role of internal oleation throughout.

Sushruta Samhita^[46]

Sushruta recommends treatment only for those patients who are non-emaciated, follow proper dietetic and behavioral regimens, and can support the therapeutic requirements. The line of treatment begins with *Snehana* and *Swedana*, followed by *Mridu Vamana* (gentle emesis) and *Virechana*. Subsequently, *Anuvasana* and *Niruha Basti* are advised. Specific interventions like *Mastishkya*, *Shirobasti*, *Abhyanga with Anu Taila*, *Shalvana Upanaha Sweda*, and

Anuvasana with Bala Taila are emphasized. This protocol should be continued for 3–4 months consistently.

Ashtanga Sangraha^[47]

Acharya Vagbhata, in alignment with Sushruta, suggests a comprehensive approach including *Snehana*, *Swedana*, *Mridu Shodhana*, *Anuvasana* and *Asthapana Basti*. Special mention is made of *Bala Taila* for *Anuvasana Basti*. Additionally, *Kukkutirasaayana Kalpa* is prescribed for long-term rejuvenation, especially as per *Doshasangraha*.

Ashtanga Hridayam^[48]

In accordance with Charaka's approach, the *Ashtanga Hridayam* advocates *Snehana* and *Snehayukta Virechana*, underlining the importance of unctuous therapy for Vata-related disorders like *Pakshaghata*.

Table 7: Tabular Presentation of Chikitsa described in Bruhat-Traty.

Sl No.	Therapy	C.S.	S.S.	A.S.	A.H.
1	Snehan		+	+	+
2	Svedan	+	+	+	
3	Vaman		+	+	
4	Basti		+	+	
5	Mrudu Virechana		+	+	
6	Sneha Virechana	+			+
7	Mastishkya		+		
8	Shirobasti		+		
9	Abhyanga		+		
10	Upanaha		+		
11	Rasayana			+	

5) Pathya–Apathya (Diet and Lifestyle Guidelines)

Ayurvedic texts do not mention separate *Pathya* (wholesome) and *Apathya* (unwholesome) specifically for *Pakshaghata*. Therefore, the general dietary and lifestyle principles prescribed for *Vata Vyadhi* are applicable.

a) Pathya (Recommended for Vata Disorders) Ahara (Diet)^[49]

- Grain Group (Anna Varga): Kulthi, Masha, Godhuma (wheat), Raktabha Shali, one-year-old Shashtika Shali, Navina Tila
- Fruits (Phala Varga): Amla-tasting fruits, Draksha, Dadima, Jambira, Parushaka, Badara, ripe Tal, Rasala, Nagaranga, Tintidi
- Vegetables (Shaka Varga): Vartaka, Lashuna, Patola, Shigru

- Milk Products (Dugdha Varga): Ghrita, Dugdha, Kilota, Dadhi-Kurchika
- Oils (Taila Varga): Tila Taila, Rubbhu Taila, Sarshapa Taila
- Liquids (Drava Varga): Yusha (pulses soup), Vasa (fat), Majja (bone marrow), Mamsa Rasa (meat soup)
- Meat (Mamsa Varga): Gramya (domestic), Audaka (aquatic), Anupa (wetland), Jangala Mamsa (wild meat)
- Others: Matsyandika, Prasarani, Gokshura, Kshirakakoli

General Recommendations

Food and substances having *Madhura*, *Amla*, *Lavana Rasa*, *Ushna Veerya*, *Snigdha Guna* and *Brihana* or *Vrishya* qualities are most suitable.

Vihara (Lifestyle)

Includes practices like *Abhyanga*, *Parisheka*, *Swedana*, *Basti*, *Avgahana*, *Upanaha*, *Snana*, *Taila Dhara*, *Shirobasti*, *Nasya*, *Samvahana*, *Brahmacharya*.

Living in a warm, windless place with exposure to mild sunlight, using soft bedding and materials like silk and wool is advised. Use of aromatic substances like *Kesar*, *Agar*, *Tejpatra*, *Ela*, *Kooth*, *Tagar* is also beneficial.

b) Apathya (Contraindicated in Vata Disorders) Ahara (Diet)

Avoid dry, cold, and rough foods, particularly:

- Grains: Trunadhanya, Kalaya, Chanaka, Rajmasha, Yava, Mudga, and others like Kanguni, Nevar, Kuruvinda
- Fruits & Vegetables: Jambu, Tinduka, Bala Tal, Shimbi, Bimbi, Talaphalasthi Majja, Udumbar, etc.
- Liquids: Cold water, water from lakes and rivers, Shitambu
- Incompatible or unwholesome food (*Viruddhahara*, *Kshara Dravya*, *Shushka Mamsa*)
- Rasa: *Katu*, *Tikta*, *Kashaya*
- Guna: *Ruksha* (dry), *Shita* (cold)

Vihara (Activities)

Avoid: *Vyayama* (exertion), *Vyavaya* (excess sexual activity), *Atibramana*, *Prajagarana* (night- watching), *Vegavidharana* (suppressing natural urges), *Chinta*, long travel on elephants or horses, *Rakta Mokshana*.

CONCLUSION

Although *Pakshaghata* is considered a challenging condition, timely initiation of appropriate Ayurvedic therapies—particularly Panchakarma procedures and internal medications—can lead to favorable outcomes and improved self-dependence.

Incorporating modern rehabilitation approaches such as physiotherapy, occupational therapy, and vocational rehabilitation alongside classical Ayurvedic management enhances recovery and improves the patient's quality of life.

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